

“Publishing my book open access makes it easier for me to disseminate knowledge, meaning my work is more widely known across the world.”

By publishing her latest book – “Myanmar’s Education Reforms. A pathway to social justice?” – open access, Lall ensured that people in the Global South can read it, not just a handful of academics in the Global North. That means academics, policy makers, activists, the general public and the people who participated in the research, all have access to it. This was hugely important to Lall. She thinks academia should make it as easy as possible for people to access important research so that no-one is shut out and research can have maximum impact.

Lall said: “Myanmar has had a coup. Nobody can go to a bookshop, nor do they think to spend money on a book, but they will click on a link and read it.”

And they are clicking on the link, so far, the book has been downloaded 37,724 times in 173 countries, including 2,793 of those downloads happening in Myanmar.

It would have been a very different story had Lall chosen to publish with a traditional press. Access would have been very limited, particularly in the Global South.

**Professor Marie Lall,
Chair of Education and
South Asian Studies
at the UCL Institute of
Education**

Why Lall supports publishing books open access

It ensures equitable access to research and knowledge

Dissemination is greater

It stops research from being extractive

Change is more likely if policy makers and activists can access research